

STREET DANCE SHOWDOWN: ANALYZING MARKETING APPROACHES IN COMPETITION CIRCUITS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Abstract

Street dance, characterized by its passion and individualistic expression, has surged in popularity, becoming a global cultural phenomenon embraced by youth worldwide. Street dance events play a pivotal role in cultivating and showcasing this vibrant culture, drawing significant attention from enthusiasts. These events offer dancers platforms for both competition and performance while simultaneously captivating vast audiences and sponsors. Consequently, the intersection of street dance and events management has emerged as a dynamic space for marketing strategies and brand promotion.

Keywords: Street Dance, Cultural Phenomenon, Street Dance Events, Marketing, Brand Promotion.

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Street dance, as a passionate and individualistic form of dance, has rapidly gained popularity as a cultural phenomenon among young people worldwide. Street dance events, serving as important platforms for promoting and showcasing street dance culture, have received widespread attention. These events not only provide dancers with opportunities for competition and performance but also attract a large number of audiences and sponsors, making it a hot field for marketing and brand promotion.

1.2 Significance of the Study

This study aims to analyze the current status of street dance event marketing and propose effective marketing strategies to facilitate the development and promotion of street dance events. Understanding the current status and challenges faced in street dance event marketing is crucial for event organizers, dancers, brands, and sponsors. Through this study, we will explore strategies such as creating unique viewing experiences, expanding social media exposure, establishing brand partnerships and sponsor relationships, and strengthening market promotion to enhance the brand influence of street dance events, increase audience participation, and attract sponsor attention.

The research purpose is to provide effective strategies and recommendations for street dance event marketing to promote the development and promotion of street dance culture. By comprehensively analyzing existing literature, we can understand the current status of street dance events, the challenges they face, and feasible marketing strategies. The results of this study will provide practical guidance to stakeholders such as event organizers, dancers, brands, and sponsors, thus enhancing the brand influence of street dance events, increasing audience participation, and attracting sponsor attention.

1.3 Definition of Street Dance and Street Dance Events

Street dance is a dance form that originated from street culture and is typically performed in public spaces such as streets, dance halls, competitions, or other public venues. It originated in the United States in the 1970s, primarily developing in informal environments such as the streets, nightclubs, and dance halls. Street dance is characterized by freedom, improvisation, and innovation, emphasizing personal style and uniqueness ^[1].

There is no specific authoritative source for the definition and origins of street dance since it has evolved from street culture and various dance styles. However, the development and influence of street dance can be traced back to Black and Latinx communities in the United States, particularly in the Bronx and Harlem neighborhoods of New York City. In these communities, young people showcased and expressed their cultural identity and creativity through their own dances.

Street dance encompasses many different dance styles, including breaking, locking, hip-hop, popping, krumping, and more. Each style has its unique movements, techniques, and musical accompaniments. Street dance events refer to specifically organized dance competitions or contests aimed at showcasing the skills, creativity, and performance abilities of street dancers ^[3]. These events are typically organized and hosted by dance organizations, schools, communities, or professional dance teams.

Street dance events can be distinguished based on their scale, types, and participants. Here are some common types of street dance events:

Street dance championships: Usually large-scale competitions that attract street dance teams and individuals from different regions, countries, or continents. Championships are held for various dance styles, such as breaking, hip-hop, popping, and more. Judges score participants based on their technique, creativity, musicality, and performance abilities.

Street dance festivals: These events are usually street dance gatherings held at specific times and locations, attracting a large number of dance enthusiasts and audiences. Street dance festivals include performances, competitions, workshops, lectures, and social activities. They serve as platforms for the exchange and showcase of street dance culture.

Dance battles: Dance battles are a common form of street dance events where two or more dancers or dance crews engage in improvised or pre-prepared duels on stage. Dancers compete with each other by showcasing their skills, creativity, and dance styles. The winner is determined by judges or the audience based on the dancers' performances.

Group showcase events: This type of event aims to promote collaboration and teamwork among street dance teams. Each team presents a meticulously choreographed street dance performance, showcasing the team's overall strength and unique style.

1.4 Definition of Event Marketing

Event marketing is the process of promoting and driving awareness of a specific event through carefully planned, comprehensive, and targeted marketing activities. Its core objective is to attract broad participation from the target audience, increase the number of event attendees, and boost the sales of event-related products or services ^[4]. The execution of event marketing involves multiple key elements, including selecting appropriate marketing channels, creating compelling content to effectively convey the message to the target audience. Additionally, establishing strong partnerships with sponsors and collaborators is an essential aspect of event marketing, as it mutually promotes event promotion and expands its influence. Simultaneously, maximizing event exposure through media coverage and extensive publicity helps increase its visibility and attractiveness.

Event marketing also emphasizes the holistic experience of participants, ranging from the smoothness of organizational processes and the comfort of participants and audiences to the quality of stage equipment and sound systems. Enhancing participant satisfaction in all aspects contributes to the improvement of event reputation and word-of-mouth effects ^[5]. Furthermore, through data analysis and evaluation, the effectiveness of various marketing activities can be accurately understood and assessed, providing valuable guidance and optimization recommendations for future event marketing. In summary, through careful planning and execution of event marketing, events can better attract the attention and participation of the target audience, enhance their visibility, attractiveness, and influence, leading to increased participant and audience numbers, as well as improved sales of related products or services.

2. Analysis of the Current Situation of Street Dance Event Marketing

Street dance events, as vibrant and uniquely charismatic sports and cultural activities, have attracted an increasing number of young people's attention and participation ^[6]. The enthusiasm of young audiences for street dance culture and their pursuit of trendsetting individuality make them the primary target audience for street dance events. These young audiences actively engage in street dance events and further promote the exposure and influence of these events by sharing and spreading related content on social media platforms ^[7]. The successful marketing of street dance events relies on several key factors.

Firstly, social media plays a crucial role in the marketing of street dance events. Event organizers can use social platforms to publish event-related videos, photos, and updates, attracting more attention and participation ^[2]. Social media influencers have also become important partners in event marketing. Their influence and fan base can help expand the exposure of events and attract more viewers. However, street dance events face ongoing challenges. Events are usually held periodically or irregularly, so organizers need to continuously strive to maintain the interest and participation of the audience. This may require constant updates and improvements to event content, introducing new elements and innovative dance choreography to keep the audience's sense of freshness and passion.

In addition, street dance events face challenges in brand positioning ^[8]. Event organizers need to determine the uniqueness and core values of the events and position them accurately within the target audience. Through clear brand positioning, events can better attract audiences and sponsors, and establish a lasting event image. The successful organization of street dance events requires sufficient financial support. Event organizers need to seek the support of sponsors and partners to obtain economic resources and other forms of support, such as venues, prizes, and marketing. Effective marketing strategies and brand image can attract more attention and investment from sponsors.

Overall, street dance events have achieved some success in marketing but still face challenges. By fully utilizing social media, continuous innovation and improvement, clear brand positioning, and actively seeking financial support, street dance events can further consolidate their marketing position and attract more audiences and sponsors. Through collaboration with related industries such as music, fashion, and art, cross-promotion can expand the influence and appeal of street dance events. Additionally, strengthening cooperation with schools, communities, and youth organizations can promote the popularization of street dance culture and cultivate more street dance enthusiasts, which is also an effective way to enhance events. To enhance the sustainable development of street dance events, event organizers can explore diverse event formats and content, such as organizing competitions with different themes, dance workshops, and performance activities. At the same time, enhancing the professionalism and competitiveness of events can attract more talented dancers to participate and elevate the overall level and entertainment value.

Finally, strengthening marketing strategies and promotional activities for street dance events is crucial. Regular publicity campaigns, event preheating, and ticket promotions can enhance the visibility and attractiveness of events. Collaborating with the media can expand the media exposure of events and attract more coverage and attention. In conclusion, street dance events, as culturally significant activities with unique charm and broad appeal, enjoy high popularity among young people. By fully utilizing social media, continuous innovation, clear brand positioning, actively seeking financial support, and enhancing cooperation and promotion, street dance events can further enhance their marketing effectiveness and achieve greater success and influence.

3. Marketing Strategy Recommendations for Street Dance Events

Based on the analysis of the current status of street dance events, we propose a series of effective marketing strategies to enhance the brand influence, audience engagement, and sponsor attention of these events. The following are key strategies for marketing street dance events:

3.1 Create a Unique Spectator Experience

To attract audiences and leave a lasting impression, event organizers can enhance the appeal of the events by creating a unique spectator experience. This can include carefully designed stage setups, lighting effects, music selection, and the use of special effects. At the same time, innovative dance choreography and performance elements can be employed to create a distinctive and unforgettable stage atmosphere, enhancing audience engagement.

3.2 Expand Social Media Exposure

Social media is a powerful tool for promoting street dance events^[9]. Event organizers should actively utilize various social media platforms such as Instagram, YouTube, TikTok, etc., to share exciting videos, photos, and stories related to the events. Collaborating with social media influencers is also an effective way to reach a broader audience by spreading the event content through their networks. Additionally, organizers can establish dedicated social media accounts for the events to interact with the audience, share behind-the-scenes highlights, and stories of the dancers, thus increasing audience participation and loyalty.

3.3 Establish Brand Partnerships and Sponsor Relationships

Collaboration with brands and sponsors is a crucial strategy for driving the development of street dance events. Event organizers can seek partnerships with brands that align with the values of street dance culture to jointly promote the events and increase brand exposure. Collaborating with sponsors can provide the events with financial support and resources, including event venues, prizes, marketing activities, etc. The common goal of

this collaboration is to enhance brand recognition, elevate the brand influence of the events, and provide effective marketing opportunities for sponsors.

3.4 Strengthen Market Promotion

Market promotion is a key factor in ensuring the success of the events. Event organizers should develop comprehensive marketing plans, including advertising, promotional activities, media partnerships, and collaborations with relevant organizations and communities. Advertising can be utilized to promote the events on television, online platforms, and outdoor media, attracting more audience attention. Promotional activities can include press conferences, media interviews, roadshows, and community events to increase the visibility and exposure of the events. Collaboration with relevant organizations and communities is also an effective marketing approach. By partnering with cultural departments, schools, community organizations, etc., the events can align with local culture and address social needs, attracting more participants and audience members.

3.5 Create a Comprehensive Event Experience through Online and Offline Channels

To provide a comprehensive event experience, event organizers should make use of both online and offline channels. Through online channels, event information, ticket sales, and interactive communication can be provided through official event websites, mobile applications, and social media platforms. Offline channels include on-site activities and interactions such as street performances, workshops, seminars, and autograph sessions. By combining online and offline channels, a more comprehensive and enriching event experience can be created for the audience and participants, thereby increasing their engagement and loyalty.

3.6 Strengthen Collaboration with Institutions and Communities

Collaborating with cultural departments, schools, community organizations, etc., and integrating the events with local culture and social needs can attract more participants and audience members. Such collaboration can enhance the influence and engagement of the events, as well as elevate their status and recognition within the community.

By implementing the above-mentioned marketing strategies, street dance events can enhance their brand influence, attract more audiences and participants, and increase sponsor attention and support. This not only contributes to the development and promotion of street dance culture but also creates greater business opportunities and economic benefits for event organizers.

4. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the marketing status of street dance events, we draw the following conclusions: Street dance events attract a young audience, and social media has a significant impact on their promotion. Event organizers can leverage social media platforms and influencers to expand their exposure and reach a wider audience. However, these events face challenges such as sustainability, brand positioning, and fundraising. Therefore, we recommend that event organizers focus on creating a unique spectator experience, establishing brand partnerships and sponsor relationships, strengthening market promotion, and collaborating with institutions and communities. This includes creating unforgettable experiences through stage setups, lighting effects, music selection, and innovative dance choreography.

It also involves clarifying the event's positioning and values, actively seeking sponsor collaborations, increasing exposure through social media, offline promotion, and partnership activities, as well as building close collaborations with institutions and communities. By implementing these marketing strategies, street dance events

can enhance their brand influence, audience engagement, and sponsor attention, thus promoting the dissemination and development of street dance culture.

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